

Emergent Route–Charging Behavior in Mixed EV Traffic Networks via Decentralized Learning

Niloofar Aminikalibar*, Farzaneh Farhadi*, and Maria Chli*

Abstract—The rapid growth of electric vehicles (EVs) has increased the need for behavioral models that capture driver adaptation to congestion and charging constraints in mixed traffic networks where EV and non-EV vehicles share the same infrastructure. Existing transportation models typically assume drivers possess correct expectations about network conditions or impose equilibrium through fixed-point computation. In contrast, real traffic patterns arise from decentralized adaptation among heterogeneous users. This paper develops a learning-based framework in which EV and non-EV drivers interact through shared road congestion, while EV drivers additionally make charging decisions. Route and charging choices jointly determine travel times and station delays, forming a coupled transport–charging congestion system in which equilibrium arises endogenously rather than being imposed. We propose *Decentralized Q-Learning in Coupled Route–Charging Networks (DQL-RCN)*, where drivers independently learn preferred actions from experienced costs. The model incorporates travel time, charging delay, pricing, range anxiety, and both en-route and destination charging alternatives. Comparisons with Centralized Planning, Multinomial Logit, and Logit-based Stochastic User Equilibrium benchmarks show DQL-RCN stabilizes to Wardrop-consistent traffic patterns while achieving competitive efficiency and low within-group cost dispersion.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of electric vehicles (EVs) is reshaping transportation systems and placing increasing pressure on road and charging infrastructure. As EV adoption rises, charging decisions become tightly coupled with route choice, creating new congestion patterns that affect overall network performance. Reliable infrastructure planning therefore requires behavioral models that capture how drivers adapt their routing and charging decisions under congestion.

In practice, driver behavior in transportation studies is commonly modeled using static discrete-choice formulations such as multinomial logit (MNL), while more behaviorally consistent approaches employ equilibrium-based traffic assignment methods to ensure network consistency [1]–[6]. These models provide tractable representations of steady-state traffic patterns by assuming that travelers hold correct expectations about travel times and charging delays, even for network regions they have not previously experienced. However, such formulations typically abstract away the adaptive process through which decentralized drivers learn and respond to congestion over time.

In reality, drivers do not possess prior knowledge of network conditions. Instead, traffic and charging congestion

emerge from repeated interactions among heterogeneous users sharing the same road infrastructure. Importantly, EV and non-EV drivers are jointly affected by road congestion: EV charging decisions modify route flows, which in turn influence travel times experienced by all drivers. Capturing this cross-class interaction is essential for evaluating charging infrastructure deployment in mixed-fleet environments.

This paper develops a decentralized behavioral framework in which EV drivers jointly choose routes and charging options, while non-EV drivers select routes on the same congested network. Rather than imposing equilibrium conditions a priori, drivers are modeled as independent learners who adapt decisions based on experienced costs. The objective is not to optimize a dynamic control system, but to represent how decentralized drivers discover congestion-consistent behavior through experience in the absence of prior equilibrium knowledge. Through repeated interaction, stable traffic and charging patterns emerge that are empirically consistent with Wardrop-type equilibrium conditions.

At convergence, drivers with identical origin–destination pairs and preference parameters experience similar costs, resulting in low within-group cost dispersion. This provides a measurable notion of behavioral stability and within-group consistency for infrastructure assessment alongside system efficiency. The proposed framework is evaluated against classical stochastic choice and centralized planning benchmarks to assess efficiency and behavioral stability under varying EV adoption levels and charging infrastructure scenarios.

II. BACKGROUND

The integration of charging decisions into route choice fundamentally changes traffic behavior in EV-enabled transportation networks. Unlike conventional vehicles, EV users must jointly select routes and charging strategies under range constraints and heterogeneous charging availability. Charging ecosystems include both rapid en-route charging (RC) and destination charging (DC), which differ in time cost, monetary cost, accessibility, and detour requirements [7]. As a result, routing and charging decisions become intrinsically coupled, generating congestion interactions across both transportation and charging infrastructure.

Existing transportation and EV charging models commonly rely on static or equilibrium-based formulations, including discrete choice and traffic assignment approaches [5], [6], [8]. While effective for steady-state analysis, these approaches often assume fixed charging modes, accurate user expectations, or independent charging decisions. Recent

* Niloofar Aminikalibar, Farzaneh Farhadi, and Maria Chli are with the School of Computer Science and Digital Technologies, Aston University, Birmingham, UK. Emails: namin21@aston.ac.uk, f.farhadi@aston.ac.uk, m.chli@aston.ac.uk

TABLE I: Model Notation

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
$\omega \in W$	O-D pair	$m \in \mathcal{M}$	an EV driver	$m^0 \in \mathcal{M}^0$	a Non-EV driver
$l \in A$	Link index	\mathcal{N}	Set of network nodes	$r \in R_\omega$	a feasible route for ω
i	Charging station index	c_l	Capacity of link l	q_i	EVs at station i
d_l	Length of link l (miles)	L_l	Free-flow travel time on link l	λ_k	Time valuation coefficient
δ, β	BPR congestion parameters	κ_i	Number of chargers in $i \in \mathcal{N}$	ζ_k	Monetary value of range anxiety
μ	Charger service rate	Y_i	Charging fee at i	$a \in \mathcal{X}_k$	action for driver k
ξ	EV adoption rate	α	Learning rate	ε	Exploration rate

studies have incorporated behavioral heterogeneity, agent-based modeling, and factors such as range anxiety [9], [10]; however, many still simplify mixed-traffic interactions or treat congestion effects as exogenous. Consequently, existing models have limited ability to capture adaptive decentralized behavior and the coupled congestion dynamics emerging from interactions among EVs, non-EVs, road networks, and charging infrastructure.

Contributions: This paper addresses these gaps through three main contributions:

(1) *Behavioral modeling contribution.* We introduce a decentralized learning framework in which EV drivers jointly select routes and charging options within a unified decision space. Rather than imposing equilibrium conditions a priori, traffic patterns emerge from repeated adaptive interactions, enabling analysis of behavioral convergence and stability.

(2) *Network modeling contribution.* We model congestion generated by heterogeneous user classes, capturing interactions between EV and non-EV drivers sharing the same network. Road congestion and charging delays are jointly determined, and destination charging is modeled as a strategic alternative to en-route fast charging, enabling integrated analysis of transport–energy infrastructure effects.

(3) *Evaluation contribution.* Beyond system efficiency, we assess equilibrium consistency and fairness through within-group cost dispersion among drivers with identical origin–destination pairs and preferences, together with behavioral and network-level stability measures.

Together, these contributions provide a behavioral framework explaining how equilibrium-like traffic outcomes emerge from decentralized learning in mixed EV transportation networks with coupled congestion effects.

III. MODEL DESCRIPTION

We formalize a coupled route–charging decision problem in which drivers select routes and, for EV users, charging options within a congested transportation network. Road congestion and charging delays are jointly determined by aggregate driver behavior, coupling transport and charging dynamics within a unified decision framework.

A. Transportation Network and Users

The transportation network is modeled as a directed graph $G = (\mathcal{N}, A)$, where \mathcal{N} and A denote nodes and links, respectively. Each link $l \in A$ has distance d_l and capacity c_l . For each origin–destination (O-D) pair $\omega \in W$, let R_ω denote the feasible route set. Charging options include en-route rapid charging (RC) at nodes $i \in \mathcal{N}$ and destination

charging (DC). EV drivers $m \in \mathcal{M}$ choose an action (r, i) consisting of route $r \in R_\omega$ and charging location i , whereas non-EV drivers $m^0 \in \mathcal{M}^0$ choose only a route r . We denote the set of feasible actions for each driver $k \in \mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{M}^0$ by \mathcal{X}_k . EV drivers face a larger action space due to charging decisions, increasing strategic complexity.

B. Driver Cost Formulation

EV driver decisions (r, i) are evaluated through a perceived monetary cost combining travel time $F(r)$, charging fee Y_i , station delay G_i (RC), and range anxiety D_r (DC). All components are converted into monetary units using driver-specific valuation parameters λ_m (time valuation coefficient) and ζ_m (range sensitivity).

The EV cost is

$$\Phi_m(r, i) = \begin{cases} \lambda_m F(r) + \lambda_m G_i + Y_i, & i \in \mathcal{N}, \\ \lambda_m F(r) + \zeta_m D_r + Y_i, & i = DC, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where RC mode includes station delay, while DC replaces waiting time with a range-anxiety penalty. Charging time under DC is not modeled as an explicit cost because charging typically occurs during destination activities (e.g., work or shopping) and therefore does not impose an additional waiting or travel-time penalty.

Non-EV drivers experience only congestion-dependent travel cost:

$$\Phi_{m^0}(r) = \lambda_{m^0} F(r). \quad (2)$$

C. Cost Components

a) *Travel time:* Link travel time follows the Bureau of Public Roads (BPR) function:

$$\tau_l = L_l \left(1 + \delta \left(\frac{n_l}{c_l} \right)^\beta \right), \quad (3)$$

where L_l is the free-flow travel time, n_l denotes the link flow aggregating both EV and non-EV users, δ is a congestion sensitivity parameter, and β controls the nonlinearity of congestion effects. Route travel time is

$$F(r) = \sum_{l \in r} \tau_l. \quad (4)$$

b) *Station delay (RC only):* En-route charging introduces explicit waiting time, modeled as

$$G_i = \frac{q_i}{\mu_i \kappa_i}, \quad (5)$$

where q_i is station demand, μ_i the service rate per charger, and κ_i the number of chargers. Following [1], [4], [11], waiting time depends on aggregate demand relative to available charging capacity, consistent with queueing-theoretic approximations of multi-server systems (e.g., M/M/c queues).

c) *Range anxiety (DC only)*: Skipping en-route charging induces perceived battery risk modeled as a function of distance (d_l) [12]:

$$D_r = \sum_{l \in r} d_l. \quad (6)$$

This range anxiety increases with route length and acts as a behavioral deterrent against selecting longer routes without intermediate charging.

d) *Charging fee*: Charging cost at location i is denoted by Y_i , with $Y_{DC} < Y_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$, reflecting the lower tariff generally associated with slower destination charging. All EV drivers are assumed to require identical charging amounts; relaxing this assumption primarily affects equilibrium scale, rather than its qualitative.

IV. METHODOLOGY

We model driver behavior as a decentralized learning process in which EV and non-EV drivers repeatedly adapt route and charging decisions based on experienced costs. We introduce *Decentralized Q-Learning in Coupled Route-Charging Networks (DQL-RCN)*, where each driver independently learns congestion-consistent preferences through repeated interactions with the network. Since drivers repeatedly select from a fixed set of alternatives without explicit state transitions, the problem is formulated as a stateless multi-agent multi-armed bandit setting [13], [14].

Each driver is modeled as an independent learning agent. For EV drivers, an action $a = (r, i)$ represents a route-charging pair, while for non-EV drivers an action corresponds to a route choice. Realized costs depend on congestion-induced travel times and charging delays generated endogenously by aggregate driver behavior.

We adopt independent tabular Q-learning [15], [16], which reduces to a stateless update rule in the absence of evolving system states. At each iteration t , every driver $k \in \mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{M}^0$ selects an action $a \in \mathcal{X}_k$ using a decaying ε -greedy policy and observes the resulting cost $\Phi_k(a)$ defined in (1). Action values are updated as

$$Q_k^{t+1}(a) = Q_k^t(a) + \alpha(\rho_k^t - Q_k^t(a)), \quad (7)$$

where $\rho_k^t = -\Phi_k(a)$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is the learning rate. The decaying ε -greedy strategy [18] enables early exploration of alternative route-charging options while gradually stabilizing toward steady traffic and charging patterns.

A. Convergence Assessment and Wardrop Consistency

Convergence is assessed empirically through flow stabilization and Wardrop consistency rather than claimed theoretically. Aggregate link flows, congestion levels, and route-charging choices are monitored across iterations, and stability is declared when successive iterations exhibit negligible variation in flows and realized costs. After stabilization, we

additionally verify Wardrop consistency by checking that used alternatives within each homogeneous O-D group yield approximately equal minimal cost, while unused alternatives do not provide lower realized cost [19].

B. Benchmark Models

We compare DQL-RCN against three benchmark models representing centralized optimization, static stochastic choice, and stochastic user equilibrium.

a) *Centralized Planning (System Optimum)*: As an efficiency benchmark, we consider a centralized planner that jointly assigns routes and charging decisions to minimize total system cost under full knowledge of congestion and charging conditions [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\{a_k\}_{k \in \mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{M}^0}} \quad & \sum_{k \in \mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{M}^0} \Phi_k(a_k) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & a_k \in \mathcal{X}_k, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{M}^0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The problem is solved iteratively using coordinate descent and provides a lower bound on achievable system cost.

b) *Multinomial Logit (MNL)*: As a static behavioral benchmark, drivers probabilistically select route-charging alternatives according to perceived costs:

$$P_k(a) = \frac{\exp(-\theta\Phi_k(a))}{\sum_{(a') \in \mathcal{X}_k} \exp(-\theta\Phi_k(a'))}, \quad (9)$$

where θ is the cost sensitivity parameter [6]. Costs are treated as exogenous and drivers do not adapt based on realized outcomes.

c) *Logit-based Stochastic User Equilibrium (Logit-SUE)*: As a congestion-consistent benchmark [5], we consider a Logit-SUE model where travel times and charging delays depend on aggregate flows. Drivers follow the logit choice structure in (9), while equilibrium flows satisfy

$$f(a) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{M}^0} P_k(a | \mathbf{f}), \quad (10)$$

yielding a stochastic equilibrium without adaptive learning dynamics.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

This section presents the model setup and equilibrium analysis, followed by the effects of DC availability and EV adoption on congestion and system cost. We then benchmark the proposed approach against state-of-the-art methods to evaluate convergence, efficiency, and fairness.

a) *Experimental Setup*: We evaluate the proposed framework on a real intercity corridor connecting Manchester and London (Fig. 1). The network includes two O-D pairs, $\omega_1 = (\text{Manchester-London})$ and $\omega_2 = (\text{Birmingham-London})$, each with two feasible routes identified using Google Maps. Several links are shared between the O-D pairs, creating overlapping flows and asymmetric route lengths across demand groups. This structure enables evaluation of congestion interactions and heterogeneous route-charging decisions within a shared transportation network.

Fig. 1: Manchester–London Network: Numbers on links indicate distances in miles. In the baseline scenario ($\xi=50\%$), all ω_1 EV drivers select en-route charging while a majority of ω_2 EV drivers adopt destination charging.

Non-EV drivers select among two feasible routes per O–D pair. EV drivers jointly choose a route and charging option, including en-route rapid charging or destination charging. This yields nine feasible actions for ω_1 and six for ω_2 , reflecting differences in route feasibility and charging availability and increasing strategic complexity.

b) Traffic Demand and Parameters: The network contains both EV and non-EV users with an EV adoption rate of $\xi = 50\%$. Each O–D pair includes 1000 drivers (500 EV and 500 non-EV), resulting in a total of 2000 drivers. This scenario represents a high-penetration setting where charging–congestion interactions become significant while maintaining balanced demand across corridors.

All links share capacity $c_l = 1000$. Each charging station contains $\kappa_i = 30$ chargers with service rate $\mu = 3$. Charging fees are set to £30 for RC stations and £9 for DC charging.

Road congestion follows the BPR function with parameters $\delta = 0.15$ and $\beta = 4$. Free-flow travel time is defined

TABLE II: System cost under different EV adoption rates(ξ) and DC ablation (total number of drivers=2000).

Model Variant	RC mode EVs		DC mode EVs		Number of EVs	Total Cost(£)
	ω_1	ω_2	ω_1	ω_2		
$\xi=50\%$	500	158	0	342	1000	188,907
$\xi=100\%$	677	201	323	799	2000	257,494
$\xi=0\%$	0	0	0	0	0	136,308
DC ablation	500	500	0	0	1000	204,866

as $L_l = \frac{d_l}{69}$, where d_l is link distance (miles) and 69 mph represents average UK intercity speed.

Driver heterogeneity is modeled using three value-of-time (VoT) groups, with drivers classified uniformly across types:

- Low VoT: $\lambda = 10$ £/h, $\zeta = 0.17$ £/mile
- Medium VoT: $\lambda = 25$ £/h, $\zeta = 0.34$ £/mile
- High VoT: $\lambda = 40$ £/h, $\zeta = 0.68$ £/mile

The values of λ and ζ are selected based on empirical estimates reported in [12], [20]. This classification enables evaluation of within-group behavioral consistency while preserving identical decision structure across agents.

Learning parameters are fixed at learning rate $\alpha = 0.05$, initial exploration $\varepsilon = 0.3$, and $T = 3000$ learning episodes.

A. Emergent Traffic and Charging Patterns

Figure 1 illustrates the network state obtained after convergence of the DQL-RCN learning process. The learned allocation shows that all EV drivers associated with ω_1 select en-route charging, while 342 EV drivers from ω_2 adopt destination charging.

This outcome reflects differences in route length and charging trade-offs: drivers traveling along the longer Manchester–London corridor rely on en-route charging to manage range considerations, whereas shorter Birmingham–London trips allow greater substitution between RC and DC. The resulting allocation indicates that charging mode selection emerges from perceived cost trade-offs between travel time, station delay, and range anxiety within the equilibrium network state. EV demand is distributed approximately evenly across RC stations, except for the station located at node 10, which attracts fewer users due to longer detour distance relative to alternative charging locations.

Learning dynamics shown in Fig. 2 indicate stabilization of link congestion after roughly 1000 episodes. Minor fluctuations persist due to residual ε -greedy exploration and are expected under stochastic action selection.

We verified that the main conclusions are robust to moderate changes in learning rate and exploration settings ($\alpha \in \{0.03, 0.05, 0.07\}$, $\varepsilon \in \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}$), with final system cost varying by less than 0.5%.

B. Sensitivity Analysis

a) Impact of Destination Charging (DC): We compare system outcomes with and without DC availability. Allowing DC reduces total system cost by approximately 8%, decreasing aggregate cost from £204,866 (RC-only scenario) to £188,907 (baseline case), as reported in Table II. The

Fig. 2: Link congestion patterns under DQL-RCN: (a) Baseline scenario, (b) Without destination charging (DC). DC availability disperses link utilization, by shifting shorter-trip EV demand from en-route charging to destination charging.

Fig. 3: Model comparison across driver classes. Black lines indicate within-group cost variance. Across EV and non-EV drivers, O-D pairs, and value-of-time (VoT) groups, DQL-RCN yields low within-group variance comparable to Logit-based SUE. Centralized planning provides an efficiency benchmark, while DQL-RCN achieves similar system costs through decentralized learning.

availability of DC redistributes traffic across routes and alleviates congestion at fast-charging stations.

Figure 2 shows that DC availability disperses link utilization and reduces RC station congestion by shifting a substantial fraction of ω_2 EV demand from en-route stations to destination charging. When DC is removed, charging demand concentrates at RC stations, producing higher station delays and more localized congestion. This indicates that DC acts primarily as a spatial redistribution mechanism for charging demand, and excluding DC can overestimate RC congestion and bias infrastructure assessment. Table II further shows an asymmetric response across O-D pairs: ω_2 exhibits substantial substitution to DC, whereas ω_1 remains primarily reliant on RC due to trip length.

b) Impact of EV Adoption Rate(ξ): We analyzed how increasing EV adoption alters charging behavior and network performance under fixed total demand. Table II shows that under full electrification ($\xi=100\%$), a noticeable fraction of long-distance drivers also adopt DC despite higher range anxiety costs. This indicates that charging mode choice is governed by congestion trade-offs rather than strict feasibility alone: as RC waiting delays increase, some drivers accept higher perceived range risk to avoid station congestion.

The results therefore demonstrate that electrification reshapes equilibrium behavior through endogenous reallocation between charging modalities. Charging demand does not scale uniformly with EV adoption; instead, higher EV adoption amplifies behavioral differentiation across O-D

pairs and increases the importance of charging flexibility for maintaining efficient traffic patterns. Neglecting either mixed-fleet interactions or adaptive charging behavior may consequently lead to biased congestion estimates and misleading infrastructure assessments.

C. Model Comparison with State-of-The-Art Methods

We compare DQL-RCN against Multinomial Logit (MNL), Logit-based Stochastic User Equilibrium (Logit-SUE), and Centralized Planning benchmarks (figure 3) introduced in Section IV-B. Results for stochastic benchmarks are averaged over 30 random seeds.

a) System efficiency: DQL-RCN achieves system cost within approximately 3% of the centralized optimum, which represents the approximate lower bound achievable under full coordination. At the same time, DQL-RCN substantially outperforms MNL (46% lower cost) and improves upon Logit-SUE by 8%. To see these results in more details, figure 3 illustrates the average cost achieved by each model for all drivers with all O-D pair and VoT groups.

These differences are practically significant. The MNL assumption produces traffic distributions with system costs approximately 50% higher than coordinated or learning-based outcomes, implying that infrastructure planning based on static random-utility models can substantially overestimate congestion and misallocate charging capacity. In contrast, DQL-RCN captures adaptive behavioral responses, allowing efficient traffic patterns to emerge without centralized control

or imposed equilibrium computation.

b) Fairness and equilibrium consistency: In addition to efficiency, we evaluate fairness through the dispersion of experienced costs among homogeneous users sharing the same O–D pair and preference parameters. For a driver group \mathcal{G} , the within-group cost variance is defined as

$$\text{Var}_{\mathcal{G}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{G}|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{G}} (\Phi_k - \bar{\Phi}_{\mathcal{G}})^2, \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{\Phi}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the group mean cost. Lower variance indicates similar realized outcomes and consistency with Wardrop-type equilibrium behavior.

Figure 3 summarizes results across all driver groups. For high-VoT EV drivers (ω_2), DQL-RCN achieves near-zero variance ($\text{Var}_{\mathcal{G}} = 0.3$), comparable to Logit-SUE and substantially lower than Centralized Planning and MNL, which yield variances of 134 and 941, respectively. We additionally verify that no unchosen alternative offers lower realized cost beyond a small tolerance ϵ (Section IV-A). Unlike Logit-SUE, which imposes equilibrium through fixed-point computation, DQL-RCN achieves low cost dispersion endogenously through decentralized learning.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented DQL-RCN, a decentralized learning framework for joint route and charging decisions in mixed EV transportation networks. Unlike conventional traffic assignment approaches that impose equilibrium conditions through fixed-point computation or assume static driver expectations, the proposed framework models how equilibrium-like traffic patterns emerge from repeated decentralized adaptation under coupled road and charging congestion.

The results show that DQL-RCN achieves system performance within 3% of the centralized optimum while substantially outperforming myopic MNL-based behavior models and slightly improving upon Logit-SUE. Importantly, the learned traffic patterns exhibit near-zero within-group cost variance among homogeneous drivers, indicating strong behavioral consistency with Wardrop-type equilibrium conditions. The analysis further demonstrates that destination charging acts as a spatial redistribution mechanism for charging demand, and that excluding DC can significantly distort congestion estimation and infrastructure assessment.

Overall, the findings suggest that static behavioral assumptions may substantially misrepresent congestion dynamics and charging demand in mixed EV/non-EV transportation systems. By explicitly modeling adaptive decentralized behavior, DQL-RCN provides a more realistic and behaviorally grounded framework for evaluating EV charging infrastructure and transportation network performance.

Future work will extend the framework toward richer state-dependent decision settings incorporating battery state-of-charge, dynamic pricing, time-varying congestion, and stochastic charging demand. These extensions would support more realistic evaluation of large-scale charging policies and intelligent transportation planning under uncertainty.

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